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PP		Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	Yes/ No
RE		Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	Yes/ No
CO		Confidential, only for partners of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	Yes/ No

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1. Abbreviations

CC0: Creative commons zero
CERN: Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
CMR: Compact membrane reactor
CSIC: Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
DMP: Data management plan
DOI: Digital object identifier
FCS: Fuel cell system
FZJ: Forschungszentrum Jülich
H2ICE: Hydrogen internal combustion engine
ISO: International Organization for Standardization
PDF: Portable Document Format
PNG: Portable network graphics
T: Task
TRL: Technology readiness level
UPV: Universitat Politècnica de València
WP: Work package

2. Summary

This is the 2nd version of the Data Management Plan of the ALL-IN Zero project, funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement 101069888. Updates on the initial DMP are reported in Table 1. It is devised to support and regularize the management life cycle for all data that will be collected, processed, and generated during the project. This plan will outline how research data will be handled during the project, and even after the project is completed, describing what data will be collected, processed, or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. The proposed DMP will ensure that the project's activities are compliant with the Horizon Europe Open Access policy.

Table 1: Changes in the data management plan

Section name	Major changes
Data summary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Redefinition of the origin of the data in accordance with the nomenclature for the files and the deliverables
Fair data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Redefinition of the recommended metadata in accordance with ZENODO repository's input data • Redefinition of the nomenclature for the files in accordance with the nomenclature of the characteristics of the deliverables • Data released specified to be done through ZENODO platform

3. Data summary

The data generated in the ALL-IN Zero project will be classified according to the typology of the research activity it is derived from, i.e., from the origin of the data. In turn, the data will be grouped according to its typology to ensure a robust and unequivocal data structure for the project.

3.1 Origin of the data

The data required at the beginning of the project is mainly data generated by the partners previously. This includes the vehicle or propulsion system models generated in previous research activities, the data defining representative driving cycles for heavy-duty applications, and fundamental knowledge and models about the CMR operation. These data are mainly used for the activities related to the preliminary sizing of the propulsion system and the definition of the experimental activities in WP3.

The origin of the data will be mainly classified as documents/reports (R), demonstrator/pilots/prototypes (DEM), datasets/microdata (DATA), dissemination material (DEC) and other (OTHER). Each one of these groups will attend to a very specific purpose:

- R – Documentation/Reports: text documents including figures or table when applicable used to report key information of the project such as deliverables or milestones.
- DEM - Demonstrator/Pilots/Prototypes: evidence of the key activities of the project.
- DATA – Integrating:
 - Experimental setup: all the information related to the experimental facilities and equipment required to carry out the activities in WPs 5-7.

- Experimental results: all the useful results data derived from the experimental activities in WPs 5-7.
- Simulation setup: mainly software files defining the configuration of the simulations and the models used to produce the numeric results in WPs 8-10.
- Simulation results: results derived from the simulations in WPs 8-10.
- DEC – Dissemination material: all the material related to the dissemination activities, including publication, brochures, posters, presentations and everything that is susceptible of being considered useful for dissemination by the partners.
- Deliverables: the documents and datasets defined as deliverables in the Gran Agreement.
- OTHER - Documents derived from the meetings (presentations, attendance lists and minutes), templates and any other document that does not fit in the previous categories.

This origin-based structure is intended to be flexible. Therefore, additional groups will be included if, at some point, it is deemed necessary.

3.2 Datasets

For the moment, 7 different common datasets are expected to be generated for the ALL-IN Zero project where all the information and outputs of it, whether they are reports, results from research activities or dissemination materials, are compiled and accessible by all partners. Each dataset will correspond to each data origin defined in section 3.1. All the data in each dataset will contain the metadata defined in this document and will follow the FAIR principles described to maximize its readability and reusability.

3.3 Types of data

The stored data will be both primary (raw) and secondary (processed) data of different natures. It is expected that both experimental and simulation models and data, together with general documentation and dissemination material are also contained in the same repository with different classifications.

The formats of the file in which these data will be contained may be:

- Acrobat PDF 1.3 - Portable Document Format
- 7Zip format
- Comma Separated Values
- Microsoft Excel for Windows
- Microsoft Word Document
- Microsoft PowerPoint for Windows
- Portable Network Graphics
- Plain Text File
- Level 5 MAT-file format (MATLAB)

The format of each file will depend on the origin of the data. Experimental and simulation raw data will mainly be compiled in .txt or .csv files, processed results in EXCEL graphs, MATLAB files or portable network graphics (.PNG), dissemination material in PDF, PowerPoint or PNG and general documentation/deliverables in Word or PDF. Data about the experimental and the simulation setup will be done in various formats, to be defined as the project progresses.

3.4 Re-used data

The expected data output of the project is mainly research data in digital format. Most of the data used in the project will be generated as new data. Only data generated internally in the previous research activities of each partner will be re-used for the preliminary calculations required for the WP3.

3.5 Expected size

1 TB is expected, although up to 10 TB may be required depending on the amount of raw data stored and the sampling frequency of the devices used for the experimental activities, to be defined.

3.6 Data utility

The data may be mainly be useful for:

- Researchers & research communities: the experimental databases generated during the ALL-IN Zero project will serve the scientific community in general by providing data about state-of-the-art technology for the propulsion and power generation systems. In this sense, it is expected that both the experimental data generated for the H2ICE and the FCS serve those researching end-user applications while the CMR-related data serves those focused on industrial H2 production or onboard production applications.
- Industry: the results related to the feasibility of the technology concept and the realistic fuel consumption and systems size will serve as input for the industry to evaluate the potential of further investing in taking the system developed in ALL-IN Zero to higher TRL. Furthermore, it will serve to estimate the potential cost of the technology and compare it against other propulsion systems in terms of performance.
- Decision/Policy makers: the results related to the feasibility of the concept in terms of performance and life cycle emissions will serve the decision makers to evaluate the potential of this alternative and analyse the benefits of investing in the medium-to-long term in this technology.

4. Fair data

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The key data will be uploaded to ZENODO, which will assign it a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). All the datasets will have metadata describing the content and administrative, structural and reference information. The metadata recommended to be provided for each file is:

- Resource type:
 - Dataset
 - Event
 - Image
 - Lesson
 - Model
 - Other
 - Physical object
 - Poster
 - Presentation
 - Publication / Conference paper
 - Publication / Conference proceeding
 - Publication / Data paper
 - Publication / Journal article
 - Publication / Output management plan
 - Publication / Patent
 - Publication / Project deliverable
 - Publication / Project milestone
 - Publication / Software documentation
 - Publication / Other

- Software
- Video/Audio
- Workflow
- Title
- Publication date (submission)
- Creator: Name, Surnames and ORCID
- License:
 - Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
 - Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike 4.0 International
- Description
- Contributors (other authors, if any)
- Keywords
- Language
- Publisher (if any)
- Programming language (ONLY IF IT IS SOFTWARE)
- Journal article paper title (ONLY IF IT IS JOURNAL PUBLICATION)
- ISSN (ONLY IF IT IS JOURNAL PUBLICATION)
- Volume (ONLY IF IT IS JOURNAL PUBLICATION)
- Issue (ONLY IF IT IS JOURNAL PUBLICATION)
- Pages (ONLY IF IT IS JOURNAL PUBLICATION)
- Conference participation title (ONLY IF IT IS CONFERENCE)
- Place (ONLY IF IT IS CONFERENCE)
- Dates (ONLY IF IT IS CONFERENCE)
- Website (ONLY IF IT IS CONFERENCE)
- Dissemination level:
 - PU: Public
 - PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 - RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 - CO: Confidential, only for partners of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

The internal identifier for deliverables will attend to the following format:

- For deliverables: ALL-IN_ZERO_DX.X_TYPE_WPX_TX_PARTNER
- For other data the format shall be: ALL-IN_ZERO _TYPE_WPX_TX_PARTNER

Where:

- DX.X: Deliverable X.X (must be filled with the corresponding deliverable number).
- TYPE refers to the type of data. Can be R, DEM, DATA, DEC and OTHER.
 - R: Document, report.
 - DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype.
 - DATA: data sets, microdata, etc.
 - DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
 - OTHER.
- WPX: work package in which the specified file was generated.
- TX: task in which the specified file was generated.
- PARTNER: main partner responsible for the file preparation.

The metadata introduced in ZENODO will be harvestable following the capabilities of the repository.

4.2 Making data accessible

Repository

The key data to be stored as an output of the ALL-IN Zero will be uploaded to ZENODO (<https://zenodo.org/communities/all-inzero/?page=1&size=20>) and, as such, the key files will have assigned a DOI the ORCID codes of the researchers involved in their elaboration. Inside each document, the identifier of the project "101069888" will be found. The data release will be made through ZENODO in the timeline indicated in the Grant Agreement.

ZENODO is an open science repository developed by CERN through the OpenAIRE project. It contains tools for Big Data management and extended Digital Library capabilities for Open Data. Through ZENODO these Big Science tools could be effectively shared with the long-tail of research. This repository can be considered trusted since it has the certification ISO 16363 and provides DOI to each one of the documents/datasets uploaded.

Apart from this repository, the datasets will be stored in internal repositories of each partners and shared via SharePoint or through the webpage of the project.

Data

Accessing the available data will not require any specific tool since it will be made available through ZENODO ALL-IN Zero community.

The data is expected to be available from the publication of the data and for 4 years after the end of the project and it will be shared or kept confidential according to the level of disclosure specified in the Grant Agreement of the project. The data may not be temporarily shared due to Intellectual property rights and embargo periods for publishing, within the normative of the European Commission. The embargo periods for publishing may last up to 1 year after the paper is published and has its DOI for journal papers.

Metadata

Each dataset and document will have a set of metadata describing the characteristics of the information within the file. The key metadata dissemination will be made completely open under Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. It will not provide information about how to access the described dataset since this information will be provided on the webpage of the ALL-IN Zero and will not remain available after the datasets are no longer available after the project.

4.3 Making data interoperable

Vocabulary

The interoperability of the data will be made by using the most commonly known engineering thesaurus so that it can reach the scientific community and the industry.

Methodology

Each partner will be provided with the metadata to be filled for each dataset and will be responsible for associating the metadata with the data clearly, whether it is in the open-access repository or in the internal repository. Each dataset will have its associated metadata in the repositories. An "index" file will be used to define the files in each repository and the most critical metadata.

All the datasets will have defined in their metadata the other datasets it is related to. The relation between the datasets is defined in the project deliverables, mainly in the project management plan.

4.4 Increase data re-use

Licensing

It is envisaged that the Creative Commons' Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0) license will be used for the public datasets.

Methodology

The reusability of the data will be ensured by means of providing the required information in readme files, data cleaning, the definitions of the recorded/generated variables and their unit. The datasets will not be in the public domain unless they are part of a deliverable with a public dissemination level, as defined in the Gran Agreement of the project. Nonetheless, they will be distributed upon request to the project coordinator, provided they do not contain sensitive information.

The use of the data after the end of the project by third parties will depend on the effectiveness of the dissemination activities, but the partners will provide the public-access data to maximize the impact of the project.

The data in ZENODO will be maintained for reusability as long as the repository continues to operate.

Quality Assurance

The quality of the data to ensure its reusability will be verified by the Quality Assurance Committee. It will be composed of 1 member of each party who will be responsible for reviewing and verifying that the quality of the deliverables and data files complies with the standards of the European Commission, the scientific community and the industry.

5. Allocation of resources

The cost mainly contemplated for the data management plan are the open-access publication expenses which will ensure that both the scientific community and the industry can access the results of the project. The foreseen publication expenses, including both international conferences and indexed scientific journals, are 16,500€. This value, already included in the project budget, corresponds to the direct costs of publishing and disseminating 9 international conferences communication (1 pax., 500€ each), and 4 open-access journal papers (3,000€ each).

The rest of the cost associated with the management of the data is already included in the personnel cost of the project (WP2). The storage cost is not considered since it is expected to use ZENODO and internal repositories, already in place by the partners, to maintain the key files for enough time, even after the end of the project.

The partner responsible for the data management is UPV, but part of this function will be carried out between all the partners to ensure the reusability, organization, and quality of the data.

6. Data security

The data will be protected mainly by a firewall, user-password access, and all the measures integrated into the internal repositories of each institution. Only project members will have permission to access the data and external researchers will only be permitted to access the data upon filling out an access form and acceptance by the project coordinator.

The data will be preserved in the long term with ZENODO and in internal repositories. This is not

expected to imply a problem, given the low volume of data foreseen for this project.

Raw and auxiliary data will be kept in the internal repositories and shared folders for a period to be decided and then deleted.

7. Ethics

There are no identified ethical or legal issues that may have an impact on sharing the datasets and outputs of the project, but they may contain sensitive information. Therefore, the data will be reviewed prior to its dissemination and sharing. The outputs will not contain personal data other than the ORCID code and name of the authors. In case any problem arises in this aspect, the data will be anonymized here as necessary.

The ethics aspects of the data and the activities related to the project will constantly be under review as part of the WP1 “Ethics requirements” of the project. Any change in the ethical aspects affecting the handling of the data will be updated in future versions of the data management plan.

8. Other issues

At this stage, the data could be subject to any additional data management procedures, as this DMP will be used as a common framework that supersedes the individual procedures of each member of the consortium.